

THE NEED TO TRAIN PROFESSIONAL ETHICS SKILLS IN STUDENTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Abstract

The approach to ethics in the field of physical education and sports is related to education and school, being very important at every national and transnational level. The different decision-makers in the differently organized countries of the European Union need a reference so that they can have a complete picture of this important issue.

Ethics is the philosophical discipline that aims to present a justification or a moral assessment of different rules, motivations, intentions, beliefs or activities. The assessment and the formulated standards are applied to the procedures in relation to other persons and to the person himself. The main purpose of ethics is to increase the level of morality and therefore the aspiration to eliminate a variety of negative behaviors. All moral principles must be communicated from an early age by both parents and educational institutions. Schools should pay more attention, in particular, to developing appropriate attitudes among children and young people. The formation of ethical standards in the field of physical education and sports is very important because observing these standards will determine a series of very important aspects, such as: What will our sports world look like? What will be the further development of the sport? How will we see issues such as freedom, happiness, quality of life, leisure, etc. What will be man's relation to material goods and to all social phenomena? All of these issues and more depend largely on us and the individual's behaviour.

Keywords: ethics, skills, students, higher education, physical education and sports

Introduction

At present, sport is a significant social phenomenon, being encouraged by the continuous improvement in the general conceptions of life. Physical education is not limited to the formation of physical skills, as it covers a wider range of skills, some of an emotional and social nature, as well as cognitive processes, motivation and moral concepts, while having more than a recreational dimension. Involvement in various physical activities brings a type of knowledge and understanding focused on principles and concepts, such as "rules of the game", fair play and respect, tactical and physical awareness and social awareness related to personal interaction and team effort, in many of the sports. The field of physical education and sports is a generating and stimulating environment for the formation and manifestation of behaviors, able to highlight the entire repertoire of human skills, talents and attitudes. The ideal human personality can result only from the harmonization of the physical development with the intellectual and the moral one, a combination that later becomes a basic stimulus and for the activation and cultivation of aptitude resources. In some cases, behaviour no longer depends on the intellect, but on moral or educational deficiencies.

The formation of key and transversal competencies requires appropriate strategies, as well as the approach in the instructive-educational process of multidisciplinary and transdisciplinarity. In the current context in which university curricula in higher education institutions of physical education and sports are focused on the development of skills and the

establishment of individual learning plans for students, the adequacy of strategies selected by teachers to achieve expected learning outcomes becomes extremely important. Also, in the case of training the professional-sports ethics of the students from the higher education institutions, it is necessary to approach the multidisciplinary of the learning situations, complex of the specialized disciplines related to deontology and professional-sports ethics, which will allow the realization of some new learning circumstances, for the development of the general competencies targeted in the curricular and key areas, with the design of the results and of the knowledge accumulated in the real life in which the students will carry out their professional activity [1, 2].

Competence represents the student's ability to solve a certain situation, based on skills and knowledge previously acquired in the instructional-educational process. Thus, taking into account the fact that students acquire various skills in an informal or non-formal setting that can be valued, a curriculum can be developed at the decision of the higher education institution that would allow transdisciplinary approaches. Therefore, the context in which the activity of teachers takes place becomes extremely complex, and the activities of curriculum design and planning and those of evaluation, in close interdependence, must be carried out in teams, in sequences, both at the level of curricular areas and and at the level of the whole team.

Multidisciplinarity - a superior form of interdisciplinarity, consists in the overlapping of some elements of the various disciplines, which collaborate. A topic belonging to a certain field is analyzed from the perspective of several disciplines, which, however, retain its conceptual structure and independence. In the case of approaching our problem, a relevant example can be represented: the professional-sports ethics of the specialists in the field will be associated with the study of the relevant aspects from the point of view of physical education, biology, psychology and sports pedagogy [1, 3, 4].

The **aim of our research** is to reflect some aspects regarding the orientation of education towards the formation of ethical, deontological, personal, cognitive, professional, sports and social skills through the multidisciplinary approach of some topics of general interest from the curriculum specific to the curriculum “Education Sciences”. The multidisciplinary approach of the contents is a superior one, which helps to create models based on transfer and integration, for the benefit of each study discipline, and in support of a superior valorization of them, including the learning environment.

Research methodology

The scientific approach represents applied research that is based on the analytical-interpretative study and consists in the processing of the information processed from the questionnaires administered to the study participants. The research method we used is the questionnaire survey. The methodological system was supplemented with the method of analyzing the specialized bibliography; the method of systematic observation and the method of analyzing the products of learning activities.

The sample of the investigated subjects (teachers, coaches, and students from the Faculty of Pedagogy of the academic institution in Chisinau) included a number of 103 respondents, respectively 33 (teachers), 26 (coaches) and 45 (students - Cycle I and II). The age structure of the respondent categories indicates a majority of young people - about 65% (up to 35 years old), 35% of teachers and coaches (aged between 48 and 67 years old): Figure 1.

Figure 1. Age structure of respondent categories

The field of physical education, especially sports is characterized by the continuous approach of the concept of "Fair play" and which is the word that fully characterizes ethics, conduct (usually in performance sports).

It refers to the simple gestures towards the teammate, opponent, referees or spectators and to the most complex situations that involve saving (helping) an opponent who fell on the sports field, recognizing misconduct, solidarity with action, fighting doping, etc. In all cases, whether we are talking about sports or another field of activity, the categories of respondents identified that this notion implies respect for oneself, for those around, for occasional partners in the profession. Regarding the educational phenomenon, it is not enough to simply juxtapose the ideas about education from different sources, but it is necessary to interrelate and integrate all teaching approaches in an interdisciplinary scientific model, able to substantiate a specific science of education. Without the principle of interdisciplinarity, multidisciplinary is meaningless and ineffective.

Analyzing the data accumulated from the answers of the categories of respondents following the application of the set of questions, we identified the need to train professional-sports ethics, to acquire by specialists in the field of physical education and sports general and specific skills that can complete its reference on the labor market (Figure 2). Thus, scientific-teaching staff gave positive answers in a percentage of 45%, coaches over 38%, while students in a percentage of 17%. At the same time, it is important to mention that the need for ethics is an objective fact, and the observance of ethical norms intrinsically is necessary, as urgently as possible in the world of sports, if we take into account the "irresistible increase of aggression". In this sense, the opinion has already been expressed that the educator, like any practitioner, be he a doctor, an engineer, an architect, is neither possible nor allowed to carry out his profession without a serious and deep knowledge of the principles and laws that guide the realities they work with [1].

Figure 2. Graphic reflection of the answers regarding the need to train the professional-sports ethics of the specialists in the field

Moreover, the field of physical education and sports is a generating and stimulating environment for the formation and manifestation of behaviors, able to highlight the entire repertoire of human skills, talents and attitudes. The ideal human personality can result only from the harmonization of the physical development with the intellectual and the moral one, a combination that later becomes a basic stimulus and for the activation and cultivation of aptitude resources.

To the question "Do you think that the professional responsibility of the specialist in the field must be in accordance with his professional conscience?" the majority of respondents gave affirmative answers to this question (over 69%), and the negative ones constituted a percentage of 16%, and 15% of those interviewed found it difficult to answer this question (Figure 3). In the context in which we refer to the issue of practical ethics or professional ethics, the pedagogical one itself, it is certainly important to highlight some aspects regarding the moral profile of the teacher, the content and quality of his educational work.

Figure 3. Graphic reflection of the answers regarding the responsibility and professional conscience of the specialist in the field

Also, in cases where the professional conscience of the specialist in the field is not in accordance with the imperatives of professional responsibility - part of social responsibility, a state of conflict can be identified between professional performance and the norm of legal conscience. Education is carried out not only in school, in higher education institutions, in the family, but also wherever individuals are active, working together, respectively in the communities, the teams where they achieve professional or sports excellence, as the case may be. In the field of physical education and sports, the reality proves that it is not enough for the coach's misconduct to be sanctioned only morally and ethically, but it is necessary for the coach and/or teacher to be aware of the legal consequences of conduct inconsistent with professional ethics.

Another aspect that has been addressed in our research is violence in sports. Violence in sports has various causes and manifestations in the behavior of participants in such activities. It can be identified in both verbal and physical form. Violence is not just about what happens inside and/or in the sports arena during the competition. It also manifests itself outside the competitive framework aiming at both the training activities and the organizational ones.

Starting from the perceptions of sports managers and coaches about sports performance, their evolution over a period, we could see in our research (according to the scorecard developed by the committee of experts with a maximum value of 100 points) that the question with reference to the aptitude and ethical tendencies of a good athlete, or in our case of a specialist to be active in the field, among the 5 items presented in Table 1 and Figure 4 the ability to motivate and the sense of responsibility have significant values.

Table 1. Characteristics

Personal characteristics	Items	Professional characteristics	Items
Ability to cooperate	16,5	Praxiological knowledge	19
Ability to analyze and solve	15,7	Sports technical-tactical knowledge	21
Ability to motivate	30,7	Psychological training	23
Sense of responsibility	25,8	Knowledge of ethics and behavior	27
Adaptability and initiatives	11,3	Managerial training	10

Figure 4. Trends in the personal characteristics of athletes/specialists in the field

Regarding the tendencies of their professional characteristics, we can observe from Figure 5 that psychological training and the accumulation of some ethical and behavioral knowledge are necessary for the training of the specialist in the field.

Figure 5. Trends in the professional characteristics of athletes/specialists in the field

In conclusion, we can say that the training of specialists in the field of physical education and sports deepens and concretizes the analysis of the need for responsibility, ethics, motivation and behavior by placing them in the real framework of the profession, the job and the actual duties required by each position from qualified persons to occupy it. At the same time, we can mention that the meaning of professional orientation is the preparation of the individual/group

for the choice of the profession, the option and the decision to prepare for useful work and for being rewarded by the community. The process of professional training, as an act of culture specific to the capitalization of skills in activities useful to the practitioner and the community, will provide specialists in the field with the knowledge and skills necessary for the selected profession. By forming a professional-sports ethic, a way of thinking is outlined for students, their interests are redefined, their professional activity is motivated by changing their behavior according to the situations of learning, personality develops and matures in relation to the requirements of competence and performance, with deontological norms (professional ethics), with the responsibility of social affirmation through the profession.

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